

Technical and Behavioural Competencies of Library Professionals in Panjab University Chandigarh: A survey

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ABSTRACT

The professional competency includes the necessary knowledge and skills to be possessed by any professionals. It is crucial in case of LIS professionals also. These competencies are based on the values of the organization and not only sharpen the ability of the professional but also contributes to organizational success in the long run. The purpose of this paper is to review the perception, expectations, preferences and current status of two competencies (technical and behavioural) that are required by the library professionals. Technical competencies (sometimes referred to as professional competencies) are the ability of a person to do their job comparatively and on the same level as other professionals in their field. Behavioural competencies (also referred to as personal competencies) encompass knowledge, skills, attitudes, and actions that distinguish excellent performers. This paper is an attempt to map these competencies level among Library Professionals of Panjab University, Chandigarh. The study is based upon the response received by the LIS professionals (library assistants and assistant librarians) for which a structured questionnaire was prepared.

KeyTerms: Competencies, Continuous professional development, CPD, Library Professionals, Assistant Librarians, Library Assistants, Panjab University, Chandigarh

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INTRODUCTION

To enhance professional progress and define goals and objectives of an organisation a Competency profiles plays a vital role. Competencies are the characteristics employers look for in their employees. A lot of competency studies have been done to analysis need of necessary competencies to achieve fixed targets and to make the organization successful. The professional competency includes the necessary knowledge and skills to be possessed by any professionals. It is crucial in case of LIS professionals also. These competencies are based on the values of the organization and not only sharpen the ability of the professional but also contributes to organizational success in the long run. Technical and Behavioural competencies are categories of competencies. Technical competencies are professional competencies relate to technical knowledge or skills that are critical for a specific job/role to be successful.

Behavioural competencies encompass knowledge, skills, attitudes, and actions that distinguish excellent performers.

OBJECTIVES

- To understand the status and trends regarding Technical and Behavioural competencies of LIS professionals
- To identify the minor and major competencies being preferred by the LIS professionals.
- To do the comparative analysis amongst the Technical and Behavioural competencies.

SCOPE & METHODOLOGY

This paper is an attempt to map these competencies level among Library Professionals of Panjab University, Chandigarh which include 17Assistant Librarians and 26 Library Assistants working

on permanent basis. To obtain the necessary primary data, a structured questionnaire was prepared. The questionnaire comprised of 26 questions out of which, technical competencies has 12 questions and behavioural competencies has 14 questions. For calculating scores assigned by respondents multiples of 10 was taken as base. The total population for survey was 43. The authors were able to obtain data from all the (43) respondents, thus making the response rate 100%.

DATA ANALYSIS

□ Technical Competencies

Technical competencies are usually concerned with effective use of IT systems and computers, or any technical skills which are necessary for a job role. They are behaviours directly related to the nature of training and the technical proficiency required to exercise effective control. Following are the list of several technical competencies along with their scores given by library professionals.

Table 1: Technical Competencies

A	Technical Competencies	Total Score	Mean Score
A1	Basic Word Processing skills	1910	318
A2	Basic Spreadsheet skills	1780	297
A3	Basic Power Point skills	1870	312
A4	Access to a PC with internet at work place	2050	342
A5	Knowledge and understanding level of the Internet	2050	342
A6	Ability level of converting an MS Word file into PDF	1910	318
A7	Knowledge of ICT (IT) resources own by his/her work place	2040	340
A8	Provide email alert to users	1870	312
A9	Provide SMS facility service to users	1740	290
A10	Knowledge about hardware	1380	230
A11	Ability to identify and retrieve information from electronic sources	1990	332
A12	understanding and using the Intranet as an internal communication	1950	325
Total		22540	3758
Mean		1878.33	

Fig.1: Technical Competencies

Figure 1 above presents the mean scores assigned to various technical competencies. According to this figure it can be readily interpreted that the respondents have given maximum importance to the two components - "access to a PC with internet at work place" and "knowledge and understanding level of the Internet" (mean score=342). The second aspect which has gained the attention of the respondents is the aspect of 'knowledge of ICT (IT) resources own by his/her work place'

(mean score=340). The component knowledge about hardware got least score (mean score=230).

□ Behavioural Competencies

Behavioural competencies encompass knowledge, skills, attitudes, and actions that distinguish excellent performers. In order to achieve consistency of understanding across the University and to enhance discussions about work behaviours, the following definitions are provided. Select the statements that best fit the work being reviewed and discuss them with the employee when giving feedback and setting expectations.

Table 2: Behavioural Competencies

B	Behavioural Competencies	Total Scores	Mean
B1	Manage time for personal development	1690	282
B2	Continuous Professional Development (CPD) should be an integral part of the organizational responsibilities.	1770	295
B3	Willing to do further study	1730	288
B4	Attend/ Presented Paper in Conferences/ Seminars locally	1690	282
B5	Attend/ Presented Paper in Conferences/ Seminars at regional/national/international levels.	1510	252
B6	Adaptability to work in a changing environment	1850	308
B7	Analytical Skills	1810	302
B8	Recognize the value of professional networking	1890	315
B9	Commitment to Continuous Learning	1880	313
B10	Creative Skills	1900	317
B11	Conceptual thinking	1840	307
B12	Recognize the variety of users in communities at all levels of the organization and accommodating their diverse needs	1740	290
B13	Effective communication skills	1920	320
B14	Committed to lifelong learning and personal career planning	1920	320
Total		25140	4191
Mean		1795.71	

Fig. 2: Behavioural Competencies

Figure 2 above depicts that amongst the many technical competencies, 'Effective communication skills' as well as 'Committed to lifelong learning and personal career planning' received maximum preference (mean score = 320 each). They were closely followed by the competencies like "professional networking" and "Creative Skills" a having mean score of 317 and 315 respectively. The component attend/presented Paper in Conferences / Seminars at regional/national/international levels got least mean score of 252.

□ **Category wise Evaluation**

Table 3: Category wise Analysis

Category	Competencies	Mean Scores
A	Technical Competencies	1878.33
B	Behavioural Competencies	1795.71

Fig. 3 : Category wise Analyses

Table and figure 3 above reveal that library professionals have given prime significance to the category i.e. Technical

Competencies (51%). Category B i.e., Behavioural Competencies (49%) has been given less emphasis by library professionals compare to technical competences.

CONCLUSION

By analysing the competencies preferences of the library professionals it can be concluded that there is strong need to facilitate all domains of competencies with greater emphasis on technical competencies. This is very true with changing scenario where we are witnessing adoption of ICT in library products and services. Organizations can and should play a more understanding role by giving ample opportunities to their employees to attain higher level of competencies which will benefit the organization itself. For this, a more holistic approach has to be implemented to have more skilled staff with greater job satisfaction because a skilled and satisfied library professional can understand and meet the user needs in a better way.

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